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**CLINICAL AND PATHOGENETIC FEATURES OF CARDIOVASCULAR PATHOLOGY
IN ELDERLY PATIENTS AND SENILE AGE
(Literature review)**

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6558964>

ABSTRACT

Throughout the world, especially in developed countries, the absolute number and proportion of elderly (>65 years) and senile (>75 years) people are increasing. Demographers and sociologists predict that the aging of the population will continue, and by 2025 the number of people aged 60 and older will increase fivefold. One important reason for this, along with declining fertility rates, is improved treatment of cardiovascular disease, which is the leading cause of death among the elderly. The most common cardiovascular disorders in the elderly are arterial hypertension, coronary heart disease, and chronic heart failure. It was widely believed that only symptomatic treatment of cardiovascular disease in the elderly and older adults was necessary until recently. Drug intervention had little effect on the prognosis of life at this age. Meanwhile, large clinical trials convincingly testify that the age of patients is not an obstacle to active medical and surgical treatment of many CVDs. However, it is necessary to consider the peculiarities of CVD treatment in elderly and senile patients.
Keywords: old age, senile age, cardiovascular diseases, coronary heart disease, atherosclerosis, heart rhythm disorders.

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**КЛИНИКО-ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТОЙ
ПАТОЛОГИИ У ЛИЦ ПОЖИЛОГО И СТАРЧЕСКОГО ВОЗРАСТА
(Обзор литературы)**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Во всем мире, особенно в развитых странах, увеличивается абсолютное число и пропорция людей пожилого (> 65 лет) и старческого (> 75 лет) возраста. По прогнозам демографов и социологов, старение населения будет продолжаться, и к 2025 г. число лиц в возрасте 60 лет и старше увеличится в 5 раз. Одной из важных причин этого, наряду с уменьшением рождаемости, является улучшение лечения сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний, составляющих ведущую причину смерти пожилых лиц. Наиболее распространенными среди сердечно-сосудистых нарушений у пожилых являются артериальная гипертония, ишемическая болезнь сердца, хроническая сердечная недостаточность. До недавнего времени бытовало мнение о необходимости лишь симптоматического лечения сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний у пожилых и престарелых людей и о незначительном влиянии медикаментозного вмешательства на прогноз жизни в этом возрасте. Между тем крупные клинические исследования убедительно свидетельствуют, что возраст пациентов не является помехой к активному медикаментозному и хирургическому лечению многих ССЗ, однако, необходимо учитывать особенности лечения ССЗ у лиц пожилого и старческого возраста.

Ключевые слова: пожилой возраст, старческий возраст, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, ишемическая болезнь сердца, атеросклероз, нарушения ритма сердца.

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Tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini oshirish markazi,
kardiologiya va gerontologiya kafedrasini intervension
kardiologiya va aritmologiya kursi bilan. O'zbekiston.

**KEKSA YOSHDA GI BEMORLARNING YURAK-QON TOMIRLARI
PATOLOGIYASINING KLINIK-PATOGENETIK XUSUSIYATLARI.
(Adabiyot sharhi)**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Бутун дунёда, айниқса ривожланган мамлакатларда кексалар (65 ёшдан ошган) ва кекса (75 ёшдан катта) одамларнинг мутлақ сони ва улуши ортиб бормоқда. Демограф ва социологларнинг фикрича, аҳолининг қариши давом этади ва 2025 йилга бориб 60 ва ундан катта ёшдагилар сони 5 баробар ортади. Бунинг муҳим сабабларидан бири туғилишнинг камайиши билан бирга, кексалар ўлимнинг асосий сабаби бўлган юрак-қон томир касалликларини даволашнинг такомиллашганидир. Кекса ёшдаги юрак-қон томир касалликлари орасида энг кўп учрайдиган артериал гипертензия, юрак ишемик касаллиги, сурункали юрак этишмовчилиги ва бошқаларни кўрсатиш мумкин. Яқин вақтгача кекса ва қарияларда юрак-қон томир касалликларини фақат симптоматик даволаш зарурлиги ва бу ёшдаги ҳаёт прогнози дори аралашувининг аҳамияти таъсири ҳақида фикр бор эди. Шу билан бирга, йирик клиник тадқиқотлар шуни кўрсатадики, беморларнинг ёши кўплаб юрак-қон томир касалликларини фаол тиббий ва жарроҳлик даволашга тўсқинлик қилмайди, аммо кекса ва кекса беморларда юрак-қон томир касалликларини даволашнинг ўзига хос хусусиятларини ҳисобга олиш керак.

Калит сўзлар: қарилик, қарилик, юрак-қон томир касалликлари, юрак томирлари касаллиги, атеросклероз, юрак ритмининг бузилиши.

Introduction. In this regard, it became necessary to classify the age groups of the population. The European Regional Office of the World Health Organization (WHO) 1963 adopted the classification of age groups of the people, which is still valid throughout the world, particularly in

Russia. According to the age classification approved by the Congress of Gerontologists and Geriatricians, the entire population over 50 years of age is divided into four age categories: 1) mature age - 50-60 years; 2) old age - 61-74 years; 3) senile age — 75 years and more; 4) centenarians - 90 years or more [6, 13, 18, 25, 31, 34]. At the same time, the characteristic feature of the global aging of the population is an increase in the proportion of people over 75 among older people. The problem is that, at the same time, the number of people on earth is also increasing every year [4, 12, 17, 20, 30].

According to the UN, the proportion of people aged 60 and over in the world in 2015 was 20%, and by 2025 it will increase to 24% by 2050 - up to one-third. The share of the elderly population in Uzbekistan is close to the indicator of the most developed countries and significantly higher than in the middle developed countries. I am close to developed countries in terms of the dynamics of the share of the elderly population [1, 26, 27, 28].

According to statistical data in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the average life expectancy as of March 2020 is 74.6 years, while this figure for men is 71.4 years, and for women, 76.2 years. The total share of people over 6 in the republic 5 years concerning the country's total population in 2020 amounted to 4.6 % [1, 26-28].

Methods and materials: Large clinical studies show that the patient's age is not an obstacle to active conservative and surgical treatment of many CVDs and IHD. Moreover, since the absolute risk of cardiovascular complications in elderly patients is higher, treatment of CVD in this category of patients has a more significant effect than in younger patients [9, 48, 123, 137].

When examining elderly patients, seemingly contradictory patterns in the structure of identified comorbidities are revealed. However, such contradictions are easily explained and leveled with a more detailed analysis. In particular, it turns out that the older age group of patients has fewer comorbidities [5, 7, 9, 10]. This is explained by the probability of surviving to old age with many comorbidities decreases with age, i.e., Roughly speaking, “the fittest survive, or rather the healthy.” In addition, it is widely known that several chronic diseases in the elderly are quite rare compared to a younger group of patients (in particular, this applies to duodenal ulcers) [19, 29]. Finally, against the background of ongoing treatment, many diseases acquire a different clinical form. So, with many years of therapy with antianginal drugs, angina pectoris passes from a painful form to a painless one, and the same thing happens with the angina pectoris clinic after normalization of blood pressure or after invasive or non-invasive revascularization [5, 6, 7, 9, 13, 27].

In elderly patients with severe forms of chronic coronary heart disease (CHD), conservative treatment methods can not always provide adequate control of anginal symptoms of the disease and reduce the risk of coronary events. In such cases, interventional and cardiac surgery with myocardial revascularization is a non-alternative method of choice. They are the “gold” standard in treating patients with severe forms of CHD and not only relieve them of anginal symptoms but also increase survival [6, 7, 9, 13, 17]. In this regard, there are data according to which the authors argue that the operations of choice for patients of older age groups are endovascular methods, which have minimal operational risk, and also reduce the risk of developing acute myocardial infarction (MI) in the late postoperative period [1, 19, 25].

In elderly and senile patients, slowing down of electrolyte metabolism leads to disturbances in the processes of repolarization and depolarization in myocytes. Against this background, there is a slowdown in the spread of excitation along the conduction pathways from the atria to the ventricles and the duration of cardiac systole increases. Such violations are described by T. Strasser et al . according to their data, rhythm disturbances after cardiac surgery are based on degenerative changes in the cells of the atrioventricular junction, in the fibers of the common trunk, especially the left bundle branch, rhythm and conduction disturbances are detected in 85.4% of elderly patients [16, 20, 28, 30].

Research results: With the aging of the body in large arterial vessels, such structural changes as intimal sclerosis, atrophy of the muscle layer, a decrease in the number of elastic and an increase in the number of collagen fibers occur. As a result, the elasticity of the vascular wall decreases and its rigidity increases. Such changes occur against the background of a decrease in functioning

capillaries per unit of tissue volume [2, 4, 7, 8]. The intensity of transcapillary metabolism decreases in such tissues, and their oxygen supply is disrupted, leading to chronic tissue hypoxia. Electron microscopy data explain this: with age, the basement membrane of capillaries thickens, collagenization of fibrils occurs, an increase in pore diameter, and a decrease in the activity of pinocytosis. The result of the described processes is the loss of elasticity of large arteries and an increase in energy consumption for the activity of the heart. As a result, compensatory LV hypertrophy and an increase in myocardial mass occur [9, 18, 21, 26].

The disorders described above are often combined with atherocalcinosis of the aorta and valvular apparatus, which causes the risk of developing hydraulic damage to the valvular apparatus, which in turn leads to hemodynamic disruptions and, accordingly, to the development of complications, the main of which are the appearance of regurgitant flows and the formation or aggravation of valvular dysfunction [34].

Elderly patients also have involitional changes in the bronchopulmonary system. Morphologically, this is manifested in an increase in mucous membranes and a decrease in ciliated cells; in the wall of bronchioles, the number of elastic fibers decreases. The result of these morphological changes is a decrease in the activity of surfactant (surfactant-containing phospholipids), worsening of bronchial patency, and an increase in early airway closure volume and residual air volume. And due to the decrease in the alveolar-capillary surface, there is a decrease in the physiological response to hypoxia. The mobility of alveolar macrophages and neutrophils slows down, and microbial colonization of the respiratory mucosa increases. As a result, the purification of the tracheobronchial tree is disturbed, which is characterized by the so-called mucociliary clearance, bronchial patency is disturbed, stagnation of bronchial secretion in the bronchial tree occurs, and conditions are created for the development of pneumonia [3, 8, 19, 28].

With age, there are also changes in the tissues of the kidneys. This is characterized by a decrease in the number of glomeruli and nephrons and a decrease in their size, filling the intercellular space with connective tissue fibers. At the same time, the basement membrane thickens, and the length and volume of the renal tubules increase. The result of the described processes is a decrease in renal blood flow and a decrease in the glomerular filtration rate. At the same time, the concentration of creatinine in the blood can remain within normal values, and the concentration function of the kidneys decreases. These features should be taken into account when determining the nitrogen excretion function of the kidneys [9, 13, 22, 24, 25]. Although the functional reserves of the kidneys in elderly patients, under normal conditions of life, it is enough to maintain the homeostasis of the body at the physiological level, in extreme conditions or even close to them, their compensatory capabilities may not be enough, which, as a rule, leads to the development of acute renal failure of varying severity [9, 16].

Conclusion: Thus, with age, changes occur in all organs and tissues, which is associated with the aging process. The given pathophysiological changes in an aging organism may not always be a pathology at the start. Still, they inevitably contribute to the development of pathological processes, which can significantly increase the risk of non-fatal and fatal complications.

It is important to note that CVD therapeutic tactics can significantly improve the quality of life and freedom from the clinical manifestations of angina pectoris and reduce the risk of developing myocardial infarction both in the immediate and long-term periods. However, obtaining a good result largely depends on the correct, optimal treatment, considering all concomitant diseases, and the patient's adherence to the selected therapy. The literature sources often contain conflicting opinions regarding approaches to treating elderly patients. The current conservative attitude towards the contingent of patients under consideration does not allow full use of the possibilities of modern treatment methods, including surgery.

References.

1. Benvenuto LJ, Krakoff LR Morbidity and mortality of orthostatic hypotension: implications for cardiovascular disease // Am management. J. Hypertens. 2011 Vol. 24, No. 2. P. 135-144.

2. Bergman H., Ferrucci L., Guralnik J., et al. Frailty: an emerging research and clinical paradigm - issues and controversies // J. Gerontol. A biol. sci. Med. sci. 2007 Vol. 62, No. 7. P. 731-737.
3. Benetos A., Rossignol P., Cherubini A. et al. Polypharmacy in the aging patient: management of hypertension in octogenarians // JAMA. 2015. Vol. 314. P. 170-180.
4. 8. Blacher J., Halimi JM, Hanon O. et al.; French Society of Hypertension. Management of hypertension in adults: the 2013 French Society of Hypertension guidelines // Fundam. Clin. Pharmacol. 2014. Vol. 28. P. 1-9.
5. Bouhanick B., Meliani S., Doucet J. et al. Gerodiab Study group. Orthostatic hypotension is associated with more severe hypertension in elderly autonomous diabetic patients from the French Gerodiab study at inclusion // Ann. cardiol. Angelol. (Paris). 2014. Vol. 63, No. 3. P. 176-182.
6. Cesari M., Gambassi G., Van Kan GA et al. The frailty phenotype and the frailty index: different instruments for different purposes // Age Aging. 2014. Vol. 43, N 1. P. 10-12.
7. Abdukadirova N.M., Kurbanov N.B., Tulaboeva G.M., Talipova Yu.Sh., Sagatova Kh.M. Therapy of chronic heart failure with preserved left ventricular ejection fraction in older patients. // *“Journal of Theoretical and Clinical Medicine”*, No. 1, 2022 From 57-63 .
8. Aronow WS, Fleg JL, Pepine CJ et al. ACCF/AHA 2011 expert consensus document on hypertension in the elderly: a report of the American College of Cardiology Foundation Task Force on Clinical Expert Consensus Documents developed in collaboration with the American Academy of Neurology, American Geriatrics Society, American Society for Preventive Cardiology, American Society of Hypertension, American Society of Nephrology, Association of Black Cardiologists, and European Society of Hypertension // J. Am. soc. hypertens. 2011 Vol. 5. P. 259-352. doi: 10.1016/j. jash.2011.06.001.
9. Beckett NS, Peters R., Fletcher AE et al.; HYVET Study Group. Treatment of hypertension in patients 80 years of age or older // N. Engl. J. Med. 2008 Vol. 358, No. 18. P. 1887-1898.
10. Benetos A., Bulpitt CJ, Petrovic M. et al. An Expert Opinion from the European society of hypertension - European union geriatric medicine society Working group on the management of hypertension in very old, frail subjects // Hypertension 2016. Vol. 67. P. 820-825. doi: 10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.115.07020.
11. Collard RM, Boter H., Schoevers RA, Oude Voshaar RC Prevalence of frailty in community-dwelling older persons: a systematic review // J. Am. Geriatr. soc. 2012. Vol. 60, No. 8. P. 1487-1492.
12. Fried LP, Ferrucci L., Darer J. et al. Untangling the concepts of disability, frailty, and comorbidity: implications for improved targeting and care // J. Gerontol. A biol. sci. Med. sci. 2014. Vol. 59, No. 3. P. 255-263.
13. Fisher A/L. Just what defines frailty? // J. Am. Geriatr. soc. 2017. Vol. 53, No. 12. P. 2229-2230.
14. Finucane C., O’Connell MD, Fan CW et al. Age-related normative changes in phasic orthostatic blood pressure in a large population study: findings from the Irish Longitudinal Study on Aging (TILDA) // Circulation. 2014. Vol. 130, No. 20. P. 1780-1789.
15. Stavenow L., Hedblad B. et al. Orthostatic hypotension predicts all-cause mortality and coronary events in middle-aged individuals (The Malmo Preventive Project) // Eur. Heart J. 2010. Vol. 31. P. 85-91.
16. Qiu C, Winblad B, Fratiglioni L. The age-dependent relation of blood pressure to cognitive function and dementia // Lancet Neurol. 2005 Vol. 4. P. 487-99.
17. Shamliyan T., Talley KM, Ramakrishnan R., Kane RL Association of frailty with survival: a systematic literature review // Ageing Res. Rev. 2013. Vol. 12, No. 2. P. 719-736.
18. Sabayan B., Oleksik AM, Maier AB et al. High blood pressure and resilience to physical and cognitive decline in the oldest: the Leiden 85-plus Study // J. Am. Geriatr. soc. 2012. Vol. 60. P. 2014-2019.
19. Senn N., Monod S. Development of a comprehensive approach for the early diagnosis of geriatric syndromes in general practice // Front. Med. (Lausanne). 2015. Vol. 2. P. 78.

20. Talipov R.M., Tulabaeva G.M., Sagatova H.M., Nurmetov H.T., Khudaiberganova N.Kh. Features of comorbidity in elderly patients with myocardial infarction Uzbek medical journal 2021 Volume 2. No. 3.
21. Talipova Yu.Sh., Nuralieva D.M., Tulaboeva G.M., Otamirzaev N.R., Kamalov B.B., Kasimova G.M., Kasimova M.S. The use of atorvastatin in the complex therapy of coronary heart disease with arterial hypertension in older patients // Journal of Theoretical and Clinical Medicine, No. 3, 2020. P 69-73
22. Taekema DG, Maier AB, Westendorp RG, de Craen AJ Higher blood pressure is associated with higher handgrip strength in the oldest old // Am. J. Hypertens. 2011 Vol. 24. P. 83-89.
23. Khokhlov R.A., Gaidashev A.E., Akhmedzhanov N.M. Predictors of atherosclerotic lesions of the arteries of the extremities according to cardioangiological screening of the adult population. Rational. pharmacotherapy in cardiology. 2015. V. 11, No. 5. S. 470-476.
24. Wilhelm-Leen ER, Hall YN, Tamura MK et al. Frailty and chronic kidney disease: the third National Health and Nutrition Evaluation Survey // Am. J. Med. 2019. Vol. 122, No. 7. P. 664-671.
25. Woo J., Yu R., Wong M. et al. Frailty Screening in the Community Using the FRAIL Scale // J. Am. Med. Dir. Assoc. 2015. Vol. 16, No. 5. P. 412-419.
26. Weber MA, Schiffrin EL, White WB et al. Clinical practice guidelines for the management of hypertension in the community a statement by the American Society of Hypertension and the International Society of Hypertension // J. Hypertens. 2014. Vol. 32. P. 3-15.
27. Warwick J., Falaschetti E., Rockwood K. et al. No evidence that frailty modifies the positive impact of antihypertensive treatment in very elderly people: an investigation of the impact of frailty upon treatment effect in the HYPertension in the Very Elderly Trial (HYVET) study, a double-blind, placebo-controlled study of antihypertensives in people with hypertension aged 80 and over // BMC Med. 2015. Vol. 13. P. 78.
28. Tulaboeva GM, Talipova Yu.Sh., Sagatova XM, Abdukodirova NM, Kosimova MA, Xusanov AA Study of the effectiveness of rosuvastatin in coronary heart disease and diabetes mellitus in older people. Nazariy va clinic Tibbiet magazine 2022 Tashkent No. 1 . From 60-66.
29. Tulaboeva G.M., Talipova Yu.Sh., Sagatova Kh.M., Azizova F.F., Nuralieva D.M. Features of electrocardiographic changes in the elderly / Educational and methodological manual, Tashkent 2020, 103 pages.
30. Tulaboeva G.M. , Talipova Yu.Sh. , Sagatova Kh.M. , Abdukodirova N.M., Kosimova M.A. , Khusanov A.A. , Kasimova M.S. The use of rosuvastatin in older patients age with coronary heart disease and diabetes . NAZARIY va KLINIK TIBBIYOT JURNALI No. 1 2022, "Journal of Theoretical and Clinical Medicine", No. 1, 2022, pp . 62-67 .
31. Tulaboeva G.M., Sagatova Kh.M., Talipova Yu.Sh. Comorbidity of depressive disorders and CVD. Monograph . Printed at: see last page ISBN: 978-620-3-04096-8 , 2020 y . 127 r.

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